

The deep-time climate archive of Svalbard (SVALGEOL 2)

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1. Introduction

Palaeoclimatology refers to the study of Earth's climate and related changes in the geological past. It typically involves the investigation of past environmental and climatic changes over a range of temporal scales—from the instantaneous to millions of years. Researchers use a variety of direct and indirect measurements to describe and quantify aspects of palaeoclimate. Examples include changes in surface temperature over time, the underlying mechanisms driving these variations, and the consequences of change.

Today, Svalbard is positioned in the High Arctic, between Arctic and Atlantic water masses, with the adjacent Fram Strait modulating water exchange and controlling both regional and global climate. Resolving changes in Svalbard's palaeogeographic position and the evolution of nearby oceanic gateways over time (Fram Strait, Western Siberian Seaway; e.g., Gaina et al. 2025) can therefore improve our understanding of global climate evolution. Svalbard offers a window into how the Earth system, including its climate, has evolved during the past, as a near-continuous rock record spanning much of the past 1000 million years is exposed on the archipelago. These sedimentary archives record past interactions between biologic, hydrologic, and geologic processes in the atmosphere, on land, and in the oceans. Thus, Svalbard's geological record provides insights into past regional as well as global climate conditions and their evolution and drivers.

The well-preserved sedimentary rock record of the Phanerozoic (spanning from 539 million years ago to the present) in Svalbard captures numerous pivotal climate transitions, along with

brief but significant climate disturbances, such as hyperthermals—events characterised by rapid and substantial warming (Figure 1). Several of these events are considered important analogues to the anthropogenic global warming that we experience today and understanding past hyperthermals provides critical insights into how the Earth system may evolve in the future (IPCC 2021). Some of the most studied events imprinted in Svalbard's sedimentary rock record include the End-Permian Mass Extinction (c. 252 million years ago—the Earth's largest mass extinction and one of its most extreme hyperthermals; e.g., Zuchuat et al. 2020), and the Palaeocene-Eocene Thermal Maximum (PETM, c. 56 million years ago; e.g., Charles et al. 2011; Jones et al. 2019). Both of these hyperthermals are being targeted by an ongoing international research project, SVALCLIME (Senger et al. 2023), that aims to core and systematically analyse the Permian to Palaeogene rock record from Svalbard.

The SVALGEOL chapter in last years' SESS report (Senger et al. 2025a) summarises the geology of Svalbard in the context of geoscientific exploration, heterogeneous data types, and multi-physical data integration across temporal and spatial scales. Smyrak-Sikora et al. (2025) provide a comprehensive overview of 148 published studies that utilise Svalbard's rock record, forming the foundation for this SESS chapter update.

In this contribution, we focus on compiling the heterogeneous datasets critical to conduct research on the deep-time palaeoclimate of Svalbard and make these available through curated and quality-controlled data packages.

Figure 1: A) Latitudinal extent of major glaciations over the past 800 million years. Figure adapted from Hoffmann (www.snowballearth.org). B) Global mean values of tropical sea surface temperatures over the last 540 Ma from Scotese et al. (2021; green curve, with shaded area 95% confidence intervals, based on oxygen isotopes from phosphatic and carbonate fossils), glaciations from Macdonald (2020); major Large Igneous Provinces recorded in Svalbard: ST–Siberian Traps, HALIP–High Arctic Large Igneous Province, NAIP–North Atlantic Igneous Province. C) Deep-time stratigraphic record in Svalbard. D) Global temperature over the last 60 Ma (modified from Westerhold et al. 2020); E) and global surface air temperature projections (mean for years 2081–2100) relative to 1850–1900 according to the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP; modified from Figure 4.35 in IPCC (2021)). Other abbreviations—LPIA: Late Palaeozoic Ice Age, EPME: End-Permian Mass Extinction, PETM: Palaeocene–Eocene Thermal Maximum, EOT: Eocene–Oligocene Transition, EAIS: East Antarctic Ice Sheet, WAIS: West Antarctic Ice Sheet, and NHIS: Northern Hemisphere Ice Sheet.

2. The state of deep-time palaeoclimate research in Svalbard

Deep-time palaeoclimate research was recently synthesised in section 2.3 of the SVALGEOL chapter (Senger et al. 2025a). We expand on that description and provide an updated discussion of Svalbard's palaeoclimate, including three new developments. First, the SVALCLIME project was submitted to the International Continental Scientific Drilling Program (ICDP) with the aim of providing a continuous drill core record from the Permian to the Palaeogene (c. 260 to 50 million years ago). Second, Senger and Jochmann (2025) presented an overview of the Svalbard Rock Vault project that aims to curate both existing and future drill cores (including those stemming from the SVALCLIME project). Third, Smyrak-Sikora et al. (2025) provided a complete overview of palaeoclimate research on Svalbard's Phanerozoic rock record that we briefly summarise here.

Smyrak-Sikora et al. (2025) highlight the significant global environmental perturbations linked to tectonic activity and large igneous province development captured by Svalbard's geological record, accessed through samples from drill cores and outcrops. Smyrak-Sikora et al. (2025) compiled data from various geological intervals and major biotic crises, from Devonian vegetation expansion to the Late Palaeozoic Ice Age, End-Permian Mass Extinction and Palaeocene-Eocene Thermal Maximum. These sedimentary and geochemical data provide insights into past climate states and climatic transitions and associated Earth system dynamics across a range of palaeolatitudes, complementing existing lower-palaeolatitude datasets.

Svalbard is currently experiencing strongly enhanced warming, with average temperatures rising approximately six times more than the global average (Hanssen-Bauer et al. 2019). This phenomenon, known as polar amplification, is well documented today but poorly resolved in the deep-time geological record. Svalbard's nearly continuous sedimentary strata, coupled with its location above the Arctic circle since the Early

Cretaceous (~125 Ma), make it an important window into deep time. When studying the past climates of Svalbard, geologists must isolate global signals for climate evolution (Figure 1) from the individual sedimentary units deposited in Svalbard and the local environmental, tectonic and geographic processes that shaped them (Figure 2). Around 400 million years ago, Svalbard was located just south of the equator at 4°S, before gradually moving northward into its Arctic position by 100 million years ago (Figure 2). The past climates that Svalbard experienced were, as discussed in detail in the SVALGEOL chapter (Senger et al. 2025a), holistically controlled through:

1. Global climate shifts
2. Long-term global tectonic influence
3. Episodic tectonic and magmatic events
4. Tectono-morphological events

In addition to its Phanerozoic records (Smyrak-Sikora et al. 2025), Svalbard also offers insights into the Tonian through Ediacaran periods of the Neoproterozoic Era (1000–538.8 Ma). These rock records provide critical insights into Neoproterozoic palaeoenvironments and biotic evolution, documenting the interplay of glaciation, sea-level change, and key developments in biotic and ecological complexity among microbial and early eukaryote (including multicellular) organisms (e.g., Mughal et al. 2025) along the northeastern Laurentian margin. The Neoproterozoic succession includes several intervals of diamictites that record global glaciation-deglaciation cycles in the “Snowball Earth” intervals of the Cryogenian Period (717 to 632 Ma; Halverson et al. 2004, 2018; Hoffman et al. 2012; Millikin et al. 2022; see summary in Smelror et al. 2025).

Outcrops at Hinlopenstretet in northeastern Spitsbergen expose a Tonian (1000 to 717 Ma) carbonate succession with stromatolites, fossilised microbial mats and a rich microfossil assemblage (Knoll et al. 1991). The lower-middle part of this succession records a prominent and

Figure 2: Plate tectonic reconstruction showing the location of Svalbard at selected timesteps extending back to 400 million years ago (Ma). The palaeolatitude for Svalbard (currently located at 78°N) is approximate and based on the global plate reconstruction of Müller et al. (2022) and palaeomagnetic reference framework of Merdith et al. (2021).

negative carbon isotope shift, globally recognised as the Bitter Springs excursion, which has been proposed to reflect eustatic sea-level fluctuations coupled with changes in nutrient delivery and ocean-circulation patterns potentially caused by inertial interchange true polar wander events (Halverson et al. 2007). These strata are overlain by a Cryogenian succession dominated by glaciomarine facies and diamictites recording the

Marinoan glaciation, intercalated with subtidal and supratidal carbonates, and overlain by Ediacaran cap carbonates (Halverson et al. 2004, 2018; Fleming et al. 2016; Fairchild et al. 2022; Millikin et al. 2022). These Neoproterozoic sequences provide a framework to link local depositional patterns in Svalbard with broader climatic, oceanographic and evolutionary changes (Halverson et al. 2018; Smelror et al. 2025).

3. Contributions to interdisciplinarity

The SVALGEOL chapter (Senger et al. 2025a) provides a holistic overview of how the geosphere contributes to interdisciplinary research across the cryosphere, biosphere, atmosphere and hydrosphere. Here we specifically focus on the contributions of deep-time palaeoclimate research to interdisciplinarity (Figure 3).

Deep-time palaeoclimate research studies the Earth system holistically—ideally integrating marine and terrestrial records to decipher how the Earth system responded to environmental perturbations (e.g., meteorite impacts, extensive volcanism) and how it recovered from such crises. These investigations are coupled with assessment of how life shaped environmental evolution or was impacted by

Figure 3: Geosphere–biosphere–atmosphere interactions over the past 4 billion years in the context of atmospheric oxygen levels. Figure modified from Wang et al. (2025).

palaeoclimate and palaeoenvironmental evolution, particularly across catastrophic events (Figure 3). Svalbard records of the End-Permian Mass Extinction, for instance, have provided key insights into not only the severity of this biotic crisis but also its protracted taxonomic and ecological recovery. Such events not only impact the geosphere, but also trigger feedback mechanisms across all surface environments. The planned SVALCLIME project

will facilitate characterisation of how the different spheres have interacted over geological timescales.

The Earth System as such links together all the five spheres (atmosphere, hydrosphere, cryosphere, biosphere, geosphere; Figure 3), and it is vital to understand how geological processes (e.g., tectonism, magmatism, uplift) influence the landscape and thereby the biosphere and the cryosphere.

4. Unanswered questions

1. The SVALGEOL chapter (Senger et al. 2025a) lists five unanswered questions related to deep-time palaeoclimate. Here we pose three additional questions:
2. Did polar amplification to global climate change occur in the geological past (Cretaceous–Palaeogene) and how can Svalbard be used to test this hypothesis?
3. How can deep-time palaeoclimate studies from Svalbard contribute to improving future climate change predictions (i.e., IPCC scenarios)?
4. How can deep-time palaeoclimate data from various sources (drill cores, outcrops, modern vs analogue data etc.) be formatted to facilitate FAIR data access and re-use?

5. Recommendations for the future

The SVALGEOL chapter (Senger et al. 2025a) provides extensive recommendations across the broad spatio-temporal scales spanning the geosciences. Here we highlight concrete recommendations with respect to deep-time palaeoclimate research:

1. Safeguarding existing drill cores and providing adequate facilities for permanent storage of new drill cores is vital and pressing at a time when the coal mining company Store Norske Spitsbergen Kulkompani has shut down its last coal mine and has virtually no active geological projects. Senger and Jochmann (2025) provided an overview of existing drill core material, and a vision of how the Svalbard Rock Vault facility may function in the future.
2. Much deep-time palaeoclimate research has been conducted on Svalbard's outcrops (Smyrak-Sikora et al. 2025). However, many of the resulting datasets are dispersed and not interconnected. We thus recommend continuing to systematically acquire digital outcrop models of key sites, where the digital outcrop model (e.g., Festningen section; Senger et al. 2022) can serve as a platform to integrate disparate data types and publications in a single coherent data package.
3. Standards should be developed to facilitate including sedimentological data (logs, proxy data etc.) in machine-readable formats at relevant data centres. Future scientific drilling (e.g., SVALCLIME) should use these standards integrated with well-designed data management plans to satisfy both primary objectives and spin-off projects.
4. The global geoscience community, in collaboration with the data management community, should strive to ensure that geoscientific data are increasingly published in FAIR, machine-actionable formats. Where appropriate, existing community standards should be adopted and extended to support interoperability and reusability between—for example, but not limited to—CF-NetCDF for geospatial measurements of environmental variables and Darwin Core for fossil and biological specimen data. In some cases, the development of new standards may be necessary for some data types or disciplinary needs; however, such efforts should proceed with caution, as the proliferation of competing standards undermines the very goal of standardisation and interoperability. Data should also be published in data centres that maximise discoverability and therefore reusability. Svalbard data, data should, where possible, be published in data centres that contribute to the SIOS Data Management System¹.

6. Data availability

In this contribution we have synthesised four important proxies for climate evolution ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, pyrolysis, mercury) in thematically organised data packages (Table 1), with temporal coverage illustrated by Figure 4. The global geoscience community should strive to make deep-time geological datasets available, adhering to the

FAIR guiding principles (i.e. findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) to facilitate global studies spanning a range of spatial and temporal scales. The Deep-Time Digital Earth programme (Wang et al. 2021) provides an overview of the current challenges and concrete possibilities for future developments.

¹ <https://sios-svalbard.org/DataSubmission>

Figure 4: Plot of the curated data packages for $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$, total organic carbon, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and Mercury (Hg) provided in the data packages (Schad and Senger 2025a,b,c,d) associated with this contribution (Table 1; Blattmann et al. 2024; Bond et al. 2015; Buggisch et al. 2012; Cui et al. 2011; Doerner et al. 2020; Dustira et al. 2013; Galfetti et al. 2007; Grasby et al. 2016; Hammer et al. 2019; Jelby et al. 2020; Jones et al. 2019; Koevoets et al. 2016, 2018; Kwon et al. 2022; Lee et al. 2019; Midtkandal et al. 2016; Mueller et al. 2014; Percival et al. 2021; Vickers et al. 2016, 2019, 2023; Wesenlund et al. 2021; Zuchuat et al. 2020). Data are provided as published in depth vs data format, but a coarse, linear depth-time relationship is applied to compare the data coverage in the Phanerozoic.

Table 1: Summary of curated and harmonised datasets with relevance for deep-time palaeoclimate research in Svalbard. Longyearbyen CO₂ lab data are provided in a data paper (Senger et al., 2025b). Parameters: $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ = carbon isotope in organic material, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ = carbon isotope in carbonate, N = Nitrogen, S = Sulphur, Hg = Mercury $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ = oxygen isotope, Pyrolysis parameters: TOC = Total Organic Carbon, S1 = quantity of free hydrocarbons (gas + oil), in mg/g of rock, S2 = quantity of thermally generated (cracked) hydrocarbons, in mg/g of rock, S3 = quantity of CO₂ generated during pyrolysis of the sample, in mg/g of rock, Tmax = Temperature in °C, at which the largest quantity of hydrocarbons is released upon cracking, PI = Production Index; PI = S1/(S1+S2), HI = Hydrogen Index in mg/g of rock, HI = (S2*100)/TOC, OI = Oxygen Index in mg/g of rock, OI = (S3*100)/TOC.

Dataset	Parameter	Period	Location	Metadata access (URL)	Dataset provider
Longyearbyen CO ₂ Lab	Various	2006 - 2025	Adventdalen	https://doi.org/10.1139/as-2024-0019	UNIS (Kim Senger, kimS@unis.no)
$\delta^{13}\text{C}$	$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$, TOC, N, S	1997 - 2024	Svalbard-wide	https://doi.org/10.11582/2025.m27ev9eu	UNIS (Simon Schad, simon.schad@posteo.de)
$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$	1997 - 2024	Svalbard-wide	https://doi.org/10.11582/2025.7l4tao47	UNIS (Simon Schad)
Pyrolysis	S1, S2, S3, TOC, Tmax, PI, HI, OI	2006 - 2024	Svalbard-wide	https://doi.org/10.11582/2025.kmemmsdj	UNIS (Simon Schad)
Mercury	Hg, TOC, Hg/TOC	2016 - 2023	Svalbard-wide	https://doi.org/10.11582/2025.9h4pe0bz	UNIS (Simon Schad)

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View south-eastwards from Kropotkinfjellet, one of the sites targeted for scientific drilling by the SvalCLIME project. (Photo: Kim Senger)

Bird's-eye view of the Festningen section in western Spitsbergen. The well-exposed coastal section spans Carboniferous to Palaeogene sediments and is the only protected geological site in Svalbard. A field guide (Mørk and Grundvåg 2020), a digital outcrop model (Senger et al. 2022) and an interactive digital introduction to the site (<https://vrsvalbard.com/the-festningen-section/>) are available. (Photo: Rafael Horota)

The deep-time climate archive of Svalbard (SVALGEOL 2)

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HIGHLIGHTS

Svalbard's rock record provides exceptional insights into past climates. An ongoing scientific drilling project, SVALCLIME, aims to drill and fully core 6 km of stratigraphy to provide a high-resolution record from 260 to 50 million years ago.

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Palaeoclimatology refers to the study of Earth's climate and related changes in the geological past. Svalbard's rocks inform geoscientists about how the Earth system has functioned over our planet's history, across timescales spanning thousands to millions of years. By better understanding past behaviour of our planet, we can more confidently predict how the global ecosystem will function in the future. It is only in the deep geological past that planet Earth had high atmospheric CO₂ concentrations similar to those we are heading towards. Svalbard provides an excellent platform for these investigations, and an ongoing scientific drilling project (SVALCLIME) aims to acquire drill cores to provide a nearly continuous climate archive from 260 to 50 million years ago (ranging in geologic age from the Permian to Palaeogene periods)—a roughly 210 million year long interval that is particularly well preserved in Svalbard's

rock record. Geoscientists can use these records to decipher how the Earth responded to major changes caused by, for instance, large-scale volcanism, meteorite impacts or the movement of continents. This chapter update provides a synthesis of Svalbard's rock record and an overview of the proxies that can be used to reconstruct past climate change and its impacts. In addition, the chapter provides curated data packages of several key palaeoenvironmental and palaeoclimate proxies (carbon and oxygen isotopes, pyrolysis and mercury) from 34 publications.

Drill core from the coal exploration borehole (borehole name 09/2005) in Urdkollen, Svalbard. The image shows 5 m of core recording the onset of the Palaeocene–Eocene Thermal Maximum (PETM; 56 Ma ago) in the Frysjaodden Formation (a specific rock unit) within the Central Spitsbergen Basin (a geological feature where the majority of coal exploration in Svalbard was focussed). (Photo: Store Norske Spitsbergen Kulkompani AS)

RECOMMENDATIONS

We recommend that:

- Existing drill cores (i.e., physical samples recovered from exploration and scientific boreholes by Store Norske Spitsbergen Kulkompani and UNIS) are permanently stored in adequate facilities in or near Longyearbyen to facilitate re-use.
- International scientific research projects (e.g., SVALCLIME) are supported to obtain continuous high-quality sedimentary records and constrain planetary evolution of environments, ecosystems and processes in the geologic past.
- The geoscience and data management communities strive to optimise the acquisition, integration, visualisation, storage and sharing of deep-time palaeoclimate data following FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) principles.
- Standards be developed to facilitate inclusion of sedimentological data (e.g., stratigraphic logs, proxy data) in machine-readable formats at relevant data centres.

Svalbard's northward motion over the past 539 million years as extracted from an optimised palaeomagnetic reference frame of Merdith et al. (2021) and Müller et al. (2022). Note that Svalbard was already located north of the Arctic circle ($66^{\circ} 34' N$) when the coal deposits around Longyearbyen were formed. (Image: Grace Shephard)